

Studies show seasonal Daylight Saving Time weakly harms health and prevents inequalities

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We revisit the association of health issues with the legislative policy of seasonal clocks (daylight saving time, summertime arrangements).

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“Careful what you wish for” is an idiom that aptly describes the interplay between sleep associations and the legislative policy of seasonal daylight saving time — seasonal DST, the biannual one-hour shift of the clocks

in autumn and in spring— during the past few years.[1–3] While the call to cancel the changing of the clocks was welcomed by many, to the horror of these associations, a plurality is now demanding a permanent summer time setting.[4] We have noted elsewhere[5, 6] that this unexpected turn of events results from a poor understanding of the policy’s aims and goals —the alignment of work hours close to sunrise and greater use of outdoor recreation in the spring-summer season[7, 8]— and a poor understanding of the natural experiments set by the policy.[9]

THE CLOCK POLICY AND MORNING LIGHT

Sleep associations perfectly explain the leading role of morning light (sunrise) to “keep us aligned with the 24-h day.”[3, 10] This role is key to argue against permanent summer time, as it would be harmful to many due to the scarcity of morning light in winter at work onset. However, this role is overlooked by sleep associations when earlier sunrise times during the spring-summer season promote earlier human activity. Indeed, the clock policy keeps the alignment of work hours close to sunrise (morning light). Note that the policy only alters human pre-set schedules, which shift from late to early (and early to late) because 8am winter time is one hour later than 8am summer time.[6] Thus, the call for permanent winter time demands to delaying the current pre-set schedules in summer, when the morning light is at its earliest.[11] Many people are saying “no, thanks, I love my current summer setting,” which translates into larger preferences for permanent summer time in polls.

ACUTE EFFECTS ARE EPIDEMIOLOGICALLY VERY WEAK

The contribution of the policy to health issues has been overstated in this discussion. Many studies reported the impact of transition dates on societal issues. The two largest studies —Janszky and Ljung [12] on Swedish myocardial infarction and Fritz *et al.* [13] on US fatal motor vehicle accidents— show a slight 5% increase of the risks in the week following the spring transition. In the case of Fritz *et al.* [13] a z -score approximately 0.3 can be assessed:[14] the impact of the spring transition is systematic, yet epidemiologically very weak.

NO STUDY REPORTS CHRONIC EFFECTS ASSOCIATED WITH SEASONAL DST

The “chronic effects” —associated with the month-long period of early activity during seasonal DST— are even more elusive, partly because there are evidences

of early summer activity and late winter activity under more naturalistic conditions, see Martín-Olalla and Mira [11], and because the effects of the seasonal policy cannot be deconfounded from pure seasonal effects. Johnson *et al.* [10] state that “[l]ater sunrises and sunsets [meaning early human activity] during [seasonal] daylight saving time are associated with increase rates of cancer, obesity, heart attacks, diabetes, suicide, and motor vehicle accidents” and cite the corresponding studies.

However, there is a significant issue with this bold statement: none of the cited studies actually analyse the impact of seasonal clocks on health. Instead they analyse the distribution of health issues according with East-West position in a time zone[15], which is to say with late-early human activity. We note in these studies that (1) the relative position of human activity remains unaltered because the seasonal clock policy is uniform across the study; (2) both the descriptor (sunset time) and the outcome (a health issue) are yearly averaged magnitudes, which prevents the attribution of the effects to the intra-year (seasonal) policy.[11] In the end, these studies report the impact on health issues of the standardization of time —the use of a uniform time in a wide area like a US time zone— and not the impact of seasonal clocks. Eventually, the comparison of effects at time zone boundaries shows evidence on the impact on health issues of a year-round one-hour shift of the clocks relative to the current setting, and may be informative when discussing permanent summer time vs permanent winter time only.

SEASONAL CLOCKS PREVENT INEQUALITIES FROM RISING

An interesting topic worthy of analysis is the fact that early risers might be more likely “negatively affected by daylight saving time, and these factors are primary drivers of potential inequalities.”[10] This idea is most true when permanent summer time is discussed. However, and perhaps counter-intuitively, seasonal clocks help to keep the number of early risers at bay better than permanent winter time and prevents health inequalities from rising. They do so by promoting early human activity only in spring and summer, when early sunrise times allow it. If seasonal clocks had not been practiced during one hundred years in UK and cities of US, then early sunrise times in spring-summer would have promoted earlier onset times; with the preference for regular year-round schedules and with the advent of cheap, efficient artificial light these earlier onset times would have persisted into the winter, resulting in larger shares of population facing dark winter mornings than today.[16] In other words, the autumn transition is crucial for preventing an increase in the number of early risers. Furthermore, an adequate setting of transition dates —early April and early October— would be very much welcomed by this group, which cur-

rently faces dark mornings after the onset and before the offset of summer time.

SEASONAL CLOCKS ARE AN ACTIVE COMPROMISE

If the clock policy is discontinued, early risers and late risers would have opposing interests. The former group would prefer permanent winter time—in line with sleep associations—because they could not sustain a further advance in their already early activity. Conversely, the latter group would prefer permanent summer time—in line with “businesses and politicians”—because they would not see reasons for a further delay of their already late activity. Can these two groups cooperate for mutual benefit? During one hundred years the long-standing policy of seasonal clocks has been an active compromise that came at the prize of biannual transition dates, but with the outcome of preventing either group from suffering month-long issues: early risers do not go too early in winter, and late risers do not go too late in summer.

After having opened a Pandora’s box, what if the best compromise we can achieve to make comfortable across seasons those who love early activity and those who love late activity continues to be the current legislative policy of seasonal clocks, which is based on the leading role of the morning light?

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

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MANUSCRIPT TIME LINE

The Authors learned of Johnson *et al.* [10] from the citations to Crawford *et al.* [3] after having crafted Martín-Olalla and Mira [9].

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